

RESEARCH ON THE EFFECT OF FLAME RETARDANTS ON THE OXYGEN INDEX OF THE EPOXY RESIN-BASED FIRE-PROTECTIVE INTUMESCENT POLYMER COATING

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Abstract. *This article studies the effect of different concentrations of flame retardants on the oxygen index of epoxy resin-based fire-resistant, bulging polymer coatings. It was found that the addition of flame retardants and chemical additives with bulging properties, in general, up to 15-20%, has a good effect on the fire resistance and bulging properties of polymer composites.*

Keywords: *flame retardants, fire retardant, epoxy resin, modifiers, polymer composite, fire retardant intumescent polymer coating.*

Introduction: In recent years, due to the extensive development of industrial sectors and a sharp increase in production volumes, great attention has been paid to the use of various effective means of protecting building structures and materials from fire, including the treatment of metal structures and materials with polymer composites, the creation of compositions for thermal insulation, fire-resistant paints and varnishes, and other materials, and the study of their properties. Determining the structural properties of buildings and structures under the influence of fire and heat on metal structures and the correct selection of fire-resistant polymer composite coatings on a scientific basis are of great importance in the organization of emergency rescue operations.

Oil and gas facilities are a source of increased explosion and fire risk as a result of the extraction, processing, transportation and storage of flammable raw materials, and special requirements are imposed on them in the field of fire safety. Reducing fire risk in production at oil and gas facilities is one of the most important tasks of ensuring the protection of people and territories from man-made threats. The implementation of measures aimed at reducing fire risk plays an important role in the system of ensuring fire safety at oil and gas facilities. In order to protect metal structures from thermal effects, convex fire retardants are often used [1; 387-6. 5; 34-43-6.].

In addition, the steel structure must be protected from external fire, withstand normal operating conditions, and be applied during production and to the protected steel structure. These requirements are met by fire protection products, the low thermal conductivity of which is based on the formation of a porous mass. Intumescent coatings are one of the most modern and developing directions in the development of composites for fire protection of metal structures [3; 433-p. 4; 424-p.].

General requirements for fire-resistant materials intended for heavy-duty steel building structures "Fire protection means for steel structures. General requirements. Method for determining the efficiency of fire resistance" GOST R 53295-2009 [5; 30 p.], but this document does not offer calculation methods for the initial assessment of optimization of rational solutions used. At the same time, the possibility of industrial methods of applying fire-fighting agents to the surface of structures requires the creation of calculation methods that allow for a rational

assessment of the fire protection of steel structures under conditions of thermal and radiation exposure [6; 47-p.].

An analysis of annual fires in Russia, the world's largest producer of oil and gas, based on statistical data on the problems of storage, processing, and transportation of oil and oil products, shows that, despite a slight decrease in their total number, the economic damage remains quite high (Figure 1) [7; pp. 5–10. 8; pp. 186–194].

Method: Today, fire-resistant polymer coatings based on wollastonite and bentonite have been created for steel structures, and various scientific studies have been conducted on their thermal performance. In buildings and structures not treated with fire-resistant, combustible polymer composite coatings, the temperature of steel-based metal structures rises to 800°C in less than 10 minutes. At this temperature, the steel structure begins to lose its integrity, because steel can only bear loads at temperatures up to 450-500°C. Based on this, the temperature lower than 450-500°C is considered important in metal constructions. Various polymer composites are used to protect metal structures from temperature effects. Their composition mainly includes phosphorus- and nitrogen-containing flame retardants, urea, melamine and ammonium polyphosphate, and minerals such as wollastonite and bentonite. Polymer coatings have good bulging properties depending on the ratio. The results show that the longer the grinding time of the coating ingredients, the higher the convexity. The results of the experiments show that the fineness of the components added to them is important in obtaining foamable polymers (Figure 1) [10; 158–166 p. 11; 110 p].

Figure 1. Cross-sectional profiles of flame retardant intumescent polymer coatings after exposure to flame.

Scientific research is being conducted by world-class scientists to produce fire-resistant, crumbly coatings modified with pentaerythritol-based flame retardants and to improve the fire resistance of metal structures.

Determination of oxygen index of polymer composites based on epoxy resins was carried out as follows.

According to it, a polymer composite sample was prepared based on GOST 12.1.044-2018 and GOST 21793-76. According to the mechanism of action of epoxy resin-based fire-protective intumescent polymer coatings, the effects of polymer binders, flame retardants, intumescent chemical additives and fillers that form gas under the influence of temperature of 200-300°C and fillers in the ratio of 5-40% on the oxygen index were studied. In addition, in this type of polymer

coating, hardeners are used in the amount of 12% compared to the mass of the polymer binder. It consists of nitrogen-containing organic compounds as hardeners.

The effect of various nitrogen and phosphorus-containing flame retardants on the oxygen index of the epoxy resin-based fire protection foamable polymer coating was studied. During the research, various ratios of the proposed compounds containing phosphorus and nitrogen, a swelling polymer composite based on epoxy resin, and a polymer composite coating with imported (pyrilax) flame retardant were compared.

The results can be analyzed by looking at Figure 2. According to it, it was determined that the oxygen index of the proportion of 20% of flame retardant in the composition of the proposed epoxy resin-based fire protection foamable polymer coating is equal to 32%. At the same time, it was analyzed in experiments that when adding more than 30% of flame retardant, the oxygen index would be 34% or higher, but due to the negative impact on the physical and mechanical properties of the polymer composite, that is, it would not meet the required standards, a ratio of 20% was found to be effective.

Figure 2. The effect of different concentrations of flame retardants on the oxygen index of the epoxy resin-based fire retardant foamable polymer coating.

Thus, the addition of chemical additives with flame retardant and swelling properties, generally up to 15-20%, to the fire resistance and swelling properties of epoxy resin-based fire-protective expanding polymer composites provides good results. It has been found that this type of polymer composite coatings can protect metal structures from the effects of temperature generated by flames.

REFERENCES

1. Novozhilov V. Non-Linear Dynamic Model of Compartment Fire Flashover // Journal of Engineering Mathematics. 2010 Vol. 67. But 4. P. 387-400.
2. Информация об авариях, произошедших на предприятиях, подконтрольных территориальным органам Федеральной службы по экологическому, технологическому, атомному надзору. УРЛ: <http://www.Rostehnadzor.ru/chronicle.html>. DOI: 10.24411/2218-130X-2017-00054 (дата обращения: 11.04.2017). С.34-43.

3. Копылов Н.П., Хасанов И.Р. Эффективность применения теплозащитных экранов для защиты от тепловых потоков при пожарах // Безопасность труда в промышленности. 2016. № 11. С. 40–42,
4. Крутолапов А.С., Чешко И.Д. Огнепреграждающие сеточные экраны для защиты технологического оборудования нефтегазопроводов // Науч.-аналит. журн. «Вестник С.-Петербурга ун-та ГПС МЧС России. 2014. №1. С. 67–72.
5. Шимко В.Ю. Использование водопленочных теплозащитных экранов для защиты от теплового излучения при горении сжиженного природного газа // Пожаровзрывобезопасность. 2013. Т. 22. № 12. С. 63–67,
6. Arhitekturnoe materialovedenie / Yu.M. Tihonov [i dr.]: ucheb. SPb.: Izd-vo Akademiya, 2013. 288 s,
7. Issledovanie povedeniya ogne-teplozashchitnykh materialov v usloviyakh pozhara / Yu.M. Tihonov [i dr.]. CH. I: Issledovaniya povedeniya ognezashchitnykh materialov na osnove vermikulita, perlita i steklofibry v usloviyakh pozhara: monografiya / pod obshch. red. V.S. Artamonova. SPb.: Asterion, 2015. 235 s
8. Страхов В.Л., Крутов А.М., Давыдкин Н.Ф. Огнезащита строительных конструкций / под ред. Ю.А. Кошмарова. М.: Информ.-изд. центр «ТИМР», 2000. 433 с.
9. Драйздел Д. Введение в динамику пожаров / под ред. Ю.А. Кошмарова, В.Е. Макарова; пер. с англ. М.: Стройиздат, 1990. 424 с.
10. ГОСТ Р 53295-2009 Группа Ж39. Национальный стандарт Российской Федерации средства огнезащиты для стальных конструкций. Общие требования. Метод определения огнезащитной эффективности. С. 30.
11. Определение категорий помещений, зданий и наружных установок по взрывопожарной и пожарной опасности НПБ 105-03. (утв. Приказом МЧС РФ от 18 июля 2003 г. № 314). Доступ из справ.-правовой системы «Гарант». 47 с.